

Why is DDC 16th called phoenix scheduled??

DDC 16th (Dewey decimal classification, 16th edition published in 1958, but the 16th abridged edition was published in 1953) is called the 'phoenix scheduled' because it rose from the ashes of the previous editions which was destroyed in a fire during world war 11.

These scheduled represent a complete re-casting of an area of the classification with little, or no reference to the editions in the 16th edition there was two related phoenix scheduled :

1. 546 Inorganic chemistry
2. 547 organic chemistry

Why is the DDC index called the relative index??

The DDC index is called the 'Relative Index' Because it indexes Subject relative to their Corresponding Classification numbers Rather than indexing The number them Selves.

Dewey said that his relative index was the most important part DDC. The name is derived from the fact this sort of index Display relationship by bringing together under the name of a concept all the notation under which it is scattered in the scheduled in the schedules the different aspects of a subject are scattered according to discipline in the relative index they are brought together under the name of a subject with their various locations in the schedules.